

Characterization of large-scale brain connectivity patterns associated with depression in Parkinson's disease

Geetha Iyer¹ , and Abdul Rauf Anwar⁴

¹Independent Researcher, India, ²University of Strasbourg, Strasbourg, France, ³Systems and Biomedical Engineering Department, Cairo University, Egypt, ⁴University Hospital RWTH Aachen, Germany

Abstract

Depression is a prevalent and disabling non-motor symptom of Parkinson's disease (PD), substantially contributing to cognitive decline and reduced quality of life. Resting-state functional MRI (rs-fMRI) provides a non-invasive approach to investigate large-scale network alterations associated with psychiatric manifestations in PD. In this study, we investigated whether resting-state connectivity patterns could serve as candidate markers of depression in PD using data from 90 participants from the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI). Connectivity was assessed using complementary seed-based connectivity (SBC), ROI-to-ROI functional connectivity, and graph-theoretical analyses across 15 regions spanning the default mode (DMN), salience (SN), and frontoparietal (FPN) networks. SBC analysis revealed significant connectivity differences between PD patients with depression (PDD) and without depression (PDND), identifying alterations involving the medial prefrontal cortex (mPFC), dorsal anterior cingulate cortex (dACC), superior parietal lobule (SPL), and supramarginal gyrus (SMG). ROI-based functional connectivity further identified convergent alterations within mPFC-centered DMN connectivity, showing negative associations between depressive symptom severity and functional connectivity measures. Based on these convergent findings, a composite DMN connectivity score was constructed, revealing a progressive decrease in connectivity across groups and significant differences between PDD and controls. Collectively, these findings highlight mPFC-centered DMN connectivity as a potential marker associated with depression in Parkinson's disease.

Keywords PPMI, seed-based connectivity, graph theory, functional connectivity, geriatric depression scale, resting-state fMRI

Published Jun 08, 2026

Source Repository

 impact-scholars/geetha-2026-pd-connectivity-analysis

Acknowledgements

We thank the Neuromatch Impact Scholar Programme, the Michael J. Fox Foundation, and the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) for supporting this work and providing access to the dataset.

Data Availability

The data used in this study were obtained from the Parkinson's Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) database (available at <https://www.ppmi-info.org/data>). The datasets are publicly and freely available to qualified investigators upon completing an online application, signing the Data User Agreement, and complying with the study's publication policies. Because the terms of the Data User Agreement strictly prohibit the unauthorized distribution of participant-level data, the authors cannot share the raw data files directly. Published via [Impact Scholars](#); original development repository.

1. INTRODUCTION

Depression is a prevalent and disabling non-motor symptom of Parkinson’s disease (PD), affecting up to 50% of patients and exacerbating motor and cognitive decline. Its multifactorial etiology involves demographic, clinical, and neurocognitive factors (Cong et al., 2022); however, the underlying neural mechanisms remain poorly understood. While motor network dysfunction in PD has been extensively characterized, depression-related connectivity alterations, particularly within the default mode and limbic networks (Morgan et al., 2018), (Xu et al., 2022), remain heterogeneous. Given this heterogeneity, we focused on large-scale resting-state networks most consistently implicated in depression, particularly the default mode network (DMN), because the DMN supports self-referential and affective processing and contains hubs, notably the medial prefrontal cortex (mPFC), that show reproducible connectivity alterations in major depression (Sheline et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2024; Zheng et al., 2026).

This study investigates resting-state connectivity as a potential marker of depression in PD using Parkinson’s Progression Markers Initiative (PPMI) data. We analyzed rs-fMRI, T1-weighted imaging, and Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS) scores from 90 participants. Functional connectivity was evaluated through seed-based and ROI-to-ROI approaches focusing on 15 regions spanning the default mode (DMN), salience (SN), and frontoparietal (FPN) networks, given their reported involvement in depression and PD. In addition, graph-theoretical analysis was employed to characterize alterations in large-scale network organization, including global integration and local segregation.

We hypothesized that depression in PD would be associated with altered large-scale network organization, particularly within the DMN, and that medial prefrontal cortex (mPFC)-centered connectivity alterations would emerge as a potential marker associated with depressive symptom severity.

2. METHODS

2.a. Data & Participants

A total of 90 participants from the [PPMI dataset](#), supported by the Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson’s Research (Marek et al., 2011), were categorized into Healthy Controls (CTRL), Parkinson’s Disease without Depression (PDND), and Parkinson’s Disease with Depression (PDD), using a Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS) threshold of ≥ 5 for the PDD group. Data included 3T rs-fMRI, T1-weighted images, demographics, and clinical metrics. To address scanner heterogeneity, we used a harmonization procedure (see [Supplementary Material](#)). Acquisition parameters were consistent across sites (TR = 2.5 s, 240 volumes), with comprehensive characteristics detailed in [Table 1](#) and [Table 2](#).

Group	N	Age (mean \pm SD)	Sex (M/F)	GDS (mean \pm SD)
CTRL	32	65.67 \pm 12.37	18/14	–
PDND	32	64.06 \pm 10.52	19/13	1.03 \pm 1.31
PDD	26	62.91 \pm 9.73	18/8	6.88 \pm 2.29

Table 1: Participant characteristics across groups

Group	Siemens	Philips	GE Medical
CTRL	24	4	4
PDND	24	4	4
PDD	18	4	4

Table 2: Distribution of participants across MRI scanner manufacturers

2.b. Preprocessing & ROI Definition

Functional and anatomical MRI data were preprocessed using the default preprocessing pipeline implemented in the CONN toolbox (CONNv25.b; (Nieto-Castanon & Whitfield-Gabrieli, 2022)), which is widely used in functional connectivity studies. Detailed preprocessing steps are provided in the [Supplementary Material](#).

Following preprocessing, 15 regions of interest (ROIs) spanning the Default Mode Network (DMN), Salience Network (SN), and Frontoparietal Network (FPN) were selected from the CONN network atlas (Table 3). These networks were chosen based on their reported involvement in cognitive and emotional processing and their relevance to non-motor symptoms in Parkinson's disease (Liao et al., 2021; Menon, 2011).

Network	Seed	x	y	z
Salience network (SAL)	Mid-cingulate cortex	0	22	35
Salience network (SAL)	Anterior insula (L)	-44	13	1
Salience network (SAL)	Anterior insula (R)	47	14	0
Salience network (SAL)	Rostral prefrontal cortex (L)	-35	45	27
Salience network (SAL)	Rostral prefrontal cortex (R)	32	46	27
Salience network (SAL)	Supramarginal gyrus (L)	-60	-39	31
Salience network (SAL)	Supramarginal gyrus (R)	62	-35	32
FrontoParietal network (FPN)	Lateral prefrontal cortex (L)	-43	33	28
FrontoParietal network (FPN)	Posterior parietal cortex (L)	-46	-58	49
FrontoParietal network (FPN)	Lateral prefrontal cortex (R)	41	38	30
FrontoParietal network (FPN)	Posterior parietal cortex (R)	52	-52	45
Default mode network (DMN)	Medial prefrontal cortex	1	55	-3
Default mode network (DMN)	Lateral parietal cortex (L)	-39	-77	33
Default mode network (DMN)	Lateral parietal cortex (R)	47	-67	29
Default mode network (DMN)	Posterior cingulate cortex	1	-61	38

Table 3: CONN toolbox network region of interest (ROI) definitions. Coordinates are reported in Montreal Neurological Institute (MNI) space. L = left hemisphere; R = right hemisphere.

2.c. Connectivity Analyses

Connectivity analyses were performed in two stages. An initial seed-based connectivity (SBC) analysis was conducted in a homogeneous subset of participants acquired using the same scanner manufacturer

(16 PDD, 20 PDND) to identify connectivity differences across groups. Subsequently, the study was extended to a larger multicenter cohort ($N = 90$, Table 2) using ComBat harmonization (see [Supplementary Material](#)), where ROI-based functional connectivity and graph analyses were performed to evaluate whether connectivity alterations were associated with depressive symptom severity (GDS).

2.c.i. Seed-Based Connectivity Analysis:

First-level seed-based connectivity maps were generated from the 15 predefined network ROIs using bivariate correlations within the CONN toolbox (CONNv25.b (Nieto-Castanon & Whitfield-Gabrieli, 2022)), followed by Fisher-Z transformation. At the second level, group-level connectivity differences were evaluated using the model:

$$SBC = \beta_1(\text{Control}) + \beta_2(\text{PDND}) + \beta_3(\text{PDD}) + \beta_4(\text{Outliers}) + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

where SBC represents seed-based connectivity strength and Control , PDND , and PDD serve as indicator variables for each diagnostic category, while Outliers accounts for the quality assurance covariate of excluded subjects. Differences across seeds were assessed using a multivariate omnibus F-test. Statistical significance was defined at voxel-level $p < 0.001$ and cluster-level FDR correction ($p_{FDR} < 0.05$) based on Gaussian Random Field theory. Detailed preprocessing steps are provided in the [Supplementary Material](#).

2.c.ii. Functional Connectivity Analysis:

ROI-based functional connectivity matrices were estimated using Pearson correlations between the predefined network ROIs and Fisher-Z transformed prior to harmonization. Associations between connectivity and depressive symptom severity were evaluated using generalized linear models implemented in Python ([Statsmodels](#)):

$$FC_{ROI} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{GDS}) + \beta_2(\text{Sex}) + \beta_3(\text{Age}) + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

where FC_{ROI} represents ROI-to-ROI functional connectivity values and GDS denotes depressive symptom severity. Multiple comparisons were controlled using FDR correction ($p_{FDR} < 0.05$). Graph-theoretical measures were subsequently derived from the harmonized connectivity matrices.

2.d. Graph-Theoretical Analysis

Subject-level weighted connectivity matrices served as inputs to construct undirected weighted graphs across the 15 ROIs. They were converted to absolute weighted matrices, and diagonal elements were set to zero. Following standard graph theory approaches (Rubinov & Sporns, 2010) and using BCTpy-0.6.1 (Brain Connectivity Toolbox), graphs were thresholded across densities from 0.10 to 0.30 in steps of 0.05, and area under the curve (AUC) values were computed across densities for all metrics. The analysis included global metrics, including weighted strength, clustering coefficient, global efficiency, and betweenness centrality, as well as local metrics, including nodal strength, clustering coefficient, betweenness centrality, participation coefficient, and within-module strength z-score to characterize regional connectivity patterns (Sporns, 2018). Group comparisons were performed using Mann–Whitney U tests with FDR correction.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

[Figure 1](#) summarizes the main findings.

Figure 1: Overview of mPFC-centered connectivity analyses

- A.** Seed-based connectivity results showing significant clusters associated with mPFC connectivity alterations. Labeled regions indicate significant clusters located in the Left Superior Parietal Lobule (SPL), dorsal Anterior Cingulate Cortex (dACC) / medial Prefrontal Cortex (mPFC), and Right Supramarginal Gyrus / Inferior Parietal Cortex. Spatial coordinates are reported in millimeters along the X, Y, and Z axes. The color bar represents F-values ($F(14, 714)$) ranging from 2.62 to 4.18.
- B.** ROI-to-ROI DMN connectivity patterns centered on the mPFC. Line colors represent GLM beta values, showing negative associations between functional connectivity and group progression. For visualization purposes, connection thickness was kept uniform across edges.
- C.** Nodal level Graph theory analysis results showing significant ROIs and their mean difference between CTRL and PDD groups based on Nodal Clustering, Nodal Participation and Within Module Strength z-score.
- D.** Distribution of DMN connectivity scores across CTRL, PD, and PDD groups. Red lines indicate group means, highlighting a progressive decrease in mPFC-centered DMN connectivity across groups.

Seed-based connectivity analysis revealed significant group-level differences between PDD and PDND, identifying four clusters of altered connectivity involving the left superior parietal lobule (SPL), medial prefrontal cortex (mPFC)/dorsal anterior cingulate cortex (dACC), right middle temporal gyrus (MTG), and right supramarginal gyrus (SMG) (Figure 1; Table 4). The primary cluster was located in the left intraparietal sulcus (IPS)/SPL (cluster size $k = 209$, $p_{FDR} = 0.001890$), while the remaining clusters involved mPFC/dACC ($k = 101$), MTG ($k = 97$), and SMG ($k = 96$; all $p_{FDR} = 0.028392$). These findings suggest altered large-scale connectivity involving the DMN, salience, and frontoparietal networks in PDD. Altered mPFC/dACC connectivity, regions implicated in self-referential and emotional processing (Levorsen et al., 2025; Yun et al., 2022), may reflect depression-related network alterations previously reported in Parkinsonian populations (Liao et al., 2021; Su et al., 2022). Altered IPS and SMG connectivity may further indicate frontoparietal reorganization associated with disrupted basal ganglia-thalamocortical circuitry (Liu et al., 2022).

ROI-based functional connectivity analysis identified convergent alterations within key DMN connections, including mPFC–left LP, mPFC–right LP, and mPFC–PCC (Figure 1; Table 5). All associations showed negative beta coefficients, indicating reduced DMN connectivity with increasing depressive symptom severity (GDS). Although these findings did not survive multiple comparison correction, they were further explored due to their consistency with previous studies reporting reduced DMN connectivity in major depressive disorder and recurrent depression (Tozzi et al., 2021; Yan et al., 2019; Yuan et al., 2011).

Graph-based analysis provided a complementary evaluation of network topology across DMN, SN, and FPN. None of the global metrics showed significance; however, exploratory nodal effects were observed in the left frontoparietal posterior parietal cortex, right DMN lateral parietal cortex, and DMN mPFC (Table 6), indicating possible alterations in cross-network participation, local segregation, and within-module integration. Although these effects did not survive FDR correction, their regional distribution aligns with previous findings demonstrating a relationship between DMN and FPN alterations and depressive symptoms in PD, as well as altered FPN modular organization in depression (Lan et al., 2022; Wei et al., 2017).

Based on the convergent SBC, ROI-based, and graph-theoretical findings centered on the mPFC, a composite DMN connectivity score was constructed to further explore DMN alterations associated with depressive symptoms. Significant group differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed between PDD and control subjects, showing a progressive decrease in DMN connectivity across groups (Figure 1; Table 7). These findings suggest that mPFC-centered DMN connectivity may represent a potential marker associated with depression in Parkinson’s disease, consistent with the established role of the mPFC in emotional processing and stress-related responses (Bittar & Labonté, 2021; Pizzagalli & Roberts, 2022).

Cluster (MNI coord)	Size (k)	p_{unc}	p_{FDR}
-36 -66 +54	209	0.000040	0.001890
-02 +26 +32	101	0.001964	0.028392
+36 -60 +18	97	0.002317	0.028392
+66 -32 +40	96	0.002416	0.028392

Table 4: Significant clusters from seed-based connectivity analysis

ROI (coord)	β	p_{unc}	p_{FDR}
DMN.MPFC arrow.r DMN.LP (L)	-0.023332	0.011707	0.892914
DMN.MPFC arrow.r DMN.LP (R)	-0.021428	0.033765	0.892914
DMN.MPFC arrow.r DMN.PCC	-0.023941	0.036295	0.892914

Table 5: Uncorrected mPFC-centered functional connectivity findings

Metric	ROI (coord)	Effect Size	p_{unc}	p_{FDR}
Nodal participation	DMN.LP (R)	-0.021308	0.032826	0.492393
Nodal clustering	FPN.PPC (L)	0.019115	0.040591	0.522919
Within-module strength z-score	DMN.MPFC	-0.011111	0.048238	0.723570

Table 6: Uncorrected graph-theoretical findings

Comparison	Test	p
Global	Kruskal-Wallis	0.0108
CTRL vs PDD	Post-hoc	0.0043
CTRL vs PDND	Post-hoc	0.0897
PDND vs PDD	Post-hoc	0.1023

Table 7: Group comparison of mPFC-centered DMN connectivity scores

4. CONCLUSION

Seed-based analysis revealed significant functional connectivity differences between PDD and PDND within DMN and frontoparietal regions in a homogeneous Siemens cohort. Extending this analysis to a larger multicenter cohort through harmonization revealed convergent trends in mPFC-centered DMN connectivity, demonstrating a negative association between depressive symptom severity (GDS) and connectivity measures. Graph-theoretical analysis supported this pattern at the regional level, showing exploratory nodal alterations in DMN and frontoparietal regions without corrected global topology differences. Furthermore, exploration using a composite DMN connectivity score demonstrated a progressive decrease in connectivity across groups, significantly differentiating PDD from control subjects.

Collectively, these findings reveal convergent evidence across seed-based, ROI-based, graph-theoretical, and composite connectivity analyses, highlighting mPFC-centered DMN alterations as a potential marker of depression in Parkinson’s disease. The progressive reduction of DMN connectivity across groups further supports the involvement of large-scale network dysfunction in depression-related processes in PD. Future studies using larger cohorts and more comprehensive brain parcellations are needed to validate its robustness and clinical utility.

5. AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Geetha Iyer performed the seed-based connectivity analyses. Rosario Huaranca conducted the ROI-to-ROI connectivity analyses. Salma Elatries performed the graph-theoretical analyses. Abdul Rauf Anwar supervised the project. All authors contributed to interpretation, manuscript preparation, and final approval.

6. SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

6.a. Preprocessing

Functional and anatomical data were preprocessed using a modular preprocessing pipeline including realignment with correction of susceptibility distortion interactions, slice timing correction, outlier detection, direct coregistration to structural, direct segmentation and MNI-space normalization, and smoothing. Functional data were realigned using SPM realign & unwarp procedure, where all scans were coregistered to a reference image (first scan of the first session) using a least squares approach and a 6 parameter (rigid body) transformation and resampled using b-spline interpolation to correct for motion and magnetic susceptibility interactions. Temporal misalignment between different slices of the functional data (acquired in interleaved Siemens order) was corrected following SPM slice-timing correction (STC) procedure, using Sinc temporal interpolation to resample each slice BOLD timeseries to a common mid-acquisition time. Potential outlier scans were identified using Artifact detection tools (ART) as acquisitions with framewise displacement above 0.9 mm or global BOLD signal changes above 5 standard deviations, and a reference BOLD image was computed for each subject by averaging all scans excluding outliers. Functional and anatomical data were coregistered using SPM intermodality coregistration procedure with a normalized mutual information objective function. Functional and anatomical data were normalized into standard MNI space, segmented into grey matter, white matter, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) tissue classes, and resampled to 2 mm isotropic voxels following a direct normalization procedure using SPM unified segmentation and normalization algorithm with the default IXI-549 tissue probability map template (Ashburner & Friston, 2005). Lastly, functional data were smoothed using spatial convolution with a Gaussian kernel of 8 mm full width half maximum (FWHM).

6.b. Denoising

In addition, functional data were denoised using a confound regression pipeline incorporating established nuisance regressors. This included the removal of potential confounding effects derived from white matter (5 regressors), CSF (5 regressors), motion parameters and their first-order derivatives (12 regressors), outlier scans (<16 regressors), session effects and their first-order derivatives (2 regressors), and linear trends (2 regressors) within each functional run, followed by bandpass frequency filtering of the BOLD timeseries between 0.01 Hz and 0.08 Hz. Component-based noise correction (CompCor) regressors were estimated within each subject's eroded white matter and CSF masks by extracting the mean signal and the largest principal components orthogonal to the mean signal, motion parameters, and outlier scans. Based on the number of nuisance regressors included, the effective temporal degrees of freedom of the denoised BOLD signal ranged from 69.3 to 74.9 (mean 74.3) across subjects.

6.c. Seed-Based Connectivity Analysis

Seed-based connectivity maps (SBC) were estimated characterizing the spatial pattern of functional connectivity with a seed area. Seed regions included 15 High-Performance Computing Independent Component Analysis (HPC-ICA) network ROIs. Functional connectivity strength was represented by Fisher-transformed bivariate correlation coefficients from a weighted general linear model (weighted-GLM), estimated separately for each seed area and target voxel, modeling the association between their BOLD signal timeseries. In order to compensate for possible transient magnetization effects at the beginning of each run, individual scans were weighted by a step function convolved with an SPM canonical hemodynamic response function and rectified. Group-level analyses were performed using a General Linear Model (GLM). For each individual voxel a separate GLM was estimated, with first-level connectivity measures at this voxel as dependent variables (one independent sample per subject and one measurement per task or experimental condition, if applicable), and groups or other subject-

level identifiers as independent variables. Voxel-level hypotheses were evaluated using multivariate parametric statistics with random-effects across subjects and sample covariance estimation across multiple measurements. Inferences were performed at the level of individual clusters (groups of contiguous voxels). Cluster-level inferences were based on parametric statistics from Gaussian Random Field theory. Results were thresholded using a combination of a cluster-forming $p < 0.001$ voxel-level threshold, and a familywise corrected $p\text{-FDR} < 0.05$ cluster-size threshold.

6.d. Harmonization

Harmonization was applied to reduce scanner-related variability in this multicenter dataset, ensuring that observed differences reflect biological rather than acquisition-related effects. In this study, harmonization was performed using the ComBat method, which corrects for systematic site-related differences in feature distributions while preserving biological variability (Orlhac et al., 2022). ComBat models the observed signal as a combination of biological effects and additive and multiplicative scanner effects:

$$y_{ij} = \alpha + \gamma_i + \delta_i \varepsilon_{ij} \quad (3)$$

where y_{ij} denotes the feature value for subject j at site i , α is the global mean, γ_i and δ_i represent additive and multiplicative site effects, and ε_{ij} is the residual error. Using a Bayesian framework, these site effects are estimated and removed to obtain harmonized values:

$$y_{ij}^{\text{ComBat}} = \frac{y_{ij} - \hat{\alpha} - \hat{\gamma}_i}{\hat{\delta}_i} + \hat{\alpha} \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{\alpha}$, $\hat{\gamma}_i$, and $\hat{\delta}_i$ are the estimated parameters. Harmonization was applied to the extracted features (e.g., connectivity measures), and the resulting data were used for subsequent statistical analyses. Implementation was performed using the NeuroHarmonize Python toolbox (Pomponio, 2026).

6.e. Graph Theory

The resulting ROI-to-ROI connectivity matrices which were harmonized were used as input. The diagonal elements of these matrices were set to zero and, although using absolute edge weights, undirected, weighted graphs were constructed using absolute edge weights which provide a measure of the magnitude of functional coupling, regardless of the correlation direction. This is important, since all of the graph metrics used in this study assume a network is weighted non-negatively.

Graph-theoretical analysis was conducted using BCTpy-0.6.1 Roan LaPlante, n.d. Graphs were proportionally thresholded across densities from 0.10 to 0.30 in steps of 0.05, and area under the curve values were computed across thresholds using trapezoidal integration. The metrics listed in the main methods were selected to characterize overall connectivity, integration, segregation, centrality, cross-network participation, and within-network integration.

Global metrics included weighted strength, clustering coefficient, global efficiency, and betweenness centrality. Local metrics included nodal strength, nodal clustering coefficient, nodal betweenness centrality, participation coefficient, and within-module strength z-score. The participation coefficient measured the level of cross-network integration, while the z-score of the within-module strength measured the strength of connection between each ROI found within its assigned module when compared to other ROIs in that module. For module-based metrics, module labels were predefined according to the CONN atlas assignments: DMN, salience network, and frontoparietal network.

Global weighted strength was calculated as:

$$S^w = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij} \quad (5)$$

where S^w denotes global weighted strength, w_{ij} is the edge weight between nodes i and j , and N is the total number of nodes.

Weighted clustering coefficient was calculated as:

$$C^w = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{k_i(k_i - 1)} \sum_{j,h} (w_{ij} \quad (6)$$

where C^w is the global clustering coefficient and k_i is the degree of node i .

Global efficiency was calculated as:

$$E_{glob} = \frac{1}{N(N - 1)} \sum_{i \neq j} \frac{1}{d_{ij}} \quad (7)$$

where E_{glob} represents global efficiency and d_{ij} is the shortest path length between nodes i and j .

Global betweenness centrality was calculated as the average nodal betweenness centrality:

$$BC = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{s \neq i \neq t} \frac{\sigma_{st}(i)}{\sigma_{st}} \quad (8)$$

where σ_{st} is the number of shortest paths between nodes s and t , and $\sigma_{st}(i)$ is the number of those paths passing through node i . The same thresholding and AUC procedure was used for local graph metrics.

Nodal strength was calculated as:

$$s_i^w = \sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij} \quad (9)$$

where s_i^w is the weighted strength of node i .

Nodal clustering coefficient was calculated as:

$$C_i^w = \frac{1}{k_i(k_i - 1)} \sum_{j,h} (w_{ij}w_{ih}w_{jh})^{1/3} \quad (10)$$

where C_i^w is the clustering coefficient of node i .

Nodal betweenness centrality was calculated as:

$$BC_i = \sum_{s \neq i \neq t} \frac{\sigma_{st}(i)}{\sigma_{st}} \quad (11)$$

where BC_i is the betweenness centrality of node i .

Participation coefficient was calculated to characterize cross-network integration:

$$P_i = 1 - \sum_{m=1}^M \left(\frac{s_{i,m}^w}{s_i^w} \right)^2 \quad (12)$$

where P_i is the participation coefficient of node i , $s_{i,m}^w$ is the strength of connections from node i to module m , s_i^w is the total nodal strength, and M is the number of predefined modules. Modules corresponded to the DMN, salience network, and frontoparietal network.

Within-module strength z-score was calculated to characterize within-network integration:

$$z_i = \frac{s_{i,m_i}^w - \mu_{m_i}}{\sigma_{m_i}} \quad (13)$$

where z_i is the within-module strength z-score of node i , s_{i,m_i}^w is the within-module strength of node i within its assigned module m_i , and μ_{m_i} and σ_{m_i} are the mean and standard deviation of within-module strengths within module m_i .

These set of metrics were selected to characterize complementary aspects of brain network organization, including overall connectivity, integration, segregation, centrality, cross-network participation, and within-network integration. Pairwise group comparisons were performed using two-sided Mann–Whitney U tests. Benjamini–Hochberg FDR correction was applied across metrics within each pairwise comparison.

REFERENCES

- Ashburner, J., & Friston, K. J. (2005). Unified segmentation. *Neuroimage*, *26*(3), 839–851. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2005.02.018>
- Bittar, T. P., & Labonté, B. (2021). Functional Contribution of the Medial Prefrontal Circuitry in Major Depressive Disorder and Stress-Induced Depressive-Like Behaviors. *Frontiers in Behavioral Neuroscience*, *15*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnbeh.2021.699592>
- Cong, S., Xiang, C., Zhang, S., Zhang, T., Wang, H., & Cong, S. (2022). Prevalence and clinical aspects of depression in Parkinson's disease: A systematic review and metaanalysis of 129 studies. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, *141*, 104749. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2022.104749>
- Lan, Z., Zhang, W., Wang, D., Tan, Z., Wang, Y., Pan, C., Xiao, Y., Kuai, C., & Xue, S.-W. (2022). Decreased modular segregation of the frontal-parietal network in major depressive disorder. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, *13*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyt.2022.929812>
- Lvorsen, M., Aoki, R., Sedikides, C., & Izuma, K. (2025). Decomposing Cognitive Processes in the mPFC during Self-Thinking. *Journal of Neuroscience*, *45*(22). <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.2378-24.2025>
- Liao, H., Cai, S., Shen, Q., Fan, J., Wang, T., Zi, Y., Mao, Z., Situ, W., Liu, J., Zou, T., Yi, J., Zhu, X., & Tan, C. (2021). Networks Are Associated With Depression in Patients With Parkinson's Disease: A Resting-State Imaging Study. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, *14*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2020.573538>
- Liu, Q., Mao, Z., Tan, C., Cai, S., Shen, Q., Wang, M., Li, J., Zhang, L., Zhou, F., Song, C., Yuan, J., Liu, Y., Liu, J., & Liao, H. (2022). Resting-state brain network in Parkinson's disease with different degrees of depression. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, *16*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2022.931365>
- Marek, K., Jennings, D., Lasch, S., Siderowf, A., Tanner, C., Simuni, T., Coffey, C., Kiebertz, K., Flagg, E., Chowdhury, S., Poewe, W., Mollenhauer, B., Klinik, P.-E., Sherer, T., Frasier, M., Meunier, C., Rudolph, A., Casaceli, C., Seibyl, J., ... Taylor, P. (2011). The Parkinson Progression Marker Initiative (PPMI). *Progress in Neurobiology*, *95*(4), 629–635. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pneurobio.2011.09.005>
- Menon, V. (2011). Large-scale brain networks and psychopathology: a unifying triple network model. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, *15*(10), 483–506. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tics.2011.08.003>
- Morgan, H. E., Ledbetter, C. R., Ferrier, C., Zweig, R. M., & Disbrow, E. A. (2018). Altered Cortico-Limbic Network Connectivity in Parkinsonian Depression: The Effect of Antidepressants. *Journal of Parkinson's Disease*, *8*(3), 429–440. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JPD-171204>
- Nieto-Castanon, & Whitfield-Gabrieli. (2022,). *CONN functional connectivity toolbox*. <https://www.hilbertpress.org/link-nieto-castanon2022>
- Pizzagalli, D. A., & Roberts, A. C. (2022). Prefrontal cortex and depression. *Neuropsychopharmacology*, *47*(1), 225–246. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41386-021-01101-7>
- Pomponio, R. (2026,). *rpomponio/neuroHarmonize*. <https://github.com/rpomponio/neuroHarmonize>
- Rubinov, M., & Sporns, O. (2010). Complex network measures of brain connectivity: Uses and interpretations. *Neuroimage*, *52*(3), 1059–1069. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuroimage.2009.10.003>

- Sheline, Y. I., Barch, D. M., Price, J. L., Rundle, M. M., Vaishnavi, S. N., Snyder, A. Z., Mintun, M. A., Wang, S., Coalson, R. S., & Raichle, M. E. (2009). The default mode network and self-referential processes in depression. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, *106*(6), 1942–1947. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0812686106>
- Sporns, O. (2018). Graph theory methods: applications in brain networks. *Dialogues in Clinical Neuroscience*, *20*(2), 111–121. <https://doi.org/10.31887/DCNS.2018.20.2/osporns>
- Su, D., Cui, Y., Liu, Z., Chen, H., Fang, J., Ma, H., Zhou, J., & Feng, T. (2022). Altered Brain Activity in Depression of Parkinson's Disease: A Meta-Analysis and Validation Study. *Frontiers in Aging Neuroscience*, *14*, 806054. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnagi.2022.806054>
- Tozzi, L., Zhang, X., Chesnut, M., Holt-Gosselin, B., Ramirez, C. A., & Williams, L. M. (2021). Reduced functional connectivity of default mode network subsystems in depression: Meta-analytic evidence and relationship with trait rumination. *Neuroimage : Clinical*, *30*, 102570. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nicl.2021.102570>
- Wei, L., Hu, X., Zhu, Y., Yuan, Y., Liu, W., & Chen, H. (2017). Aberrant Intra- and Internetwork Functional Connectivity in Depressed Parkinson's Disease. *Scientific Reports*, *7*(1), 2568. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-02127-y>
- Xu, J., Yu, M., Wang, H., Li, Y., Li, L., Ren, J., Pan, C., & Liu, W. (2022). Altered Dynamic Functional Connectivity in de novo Parkinson's Disease Patients With Depression. *Frontiers in Aging Neuroscience*, *13*, 789785. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnagi.2021.789785>
- Yan, C.-G., Chen, X., Li, L., Castellanos, F. X., Bai, T.-J., Bo, Q.-J., Cao, J., Chen, G.-M., Chen, N.-X., Chen, W., Cheng, C., Cheng, Y.-Q., Cui, X.-L., Duan, J., Fang, Y.-R., Gong, Q.-Y., Guo, W.-B., Hou, Z.-H., Hu, L., ... Zang, Y.-F. (2019). Reduced default mode network functional connectivity in patients with recurrent major depressive disorder. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, *116*(18), 9078–9083. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1900390116>
- Yuan, H., Rui, L., Jiangtao, L., & Xia, W. (2011,). *Functional connectivity comparison of the default mode network in non-depressed Parkinson disease and depressed Parkinson disease*.
- Yun, J.-Y., Lee, Y. I., Park, S., Choi, J. M., Choi, S.-H., & Jang, J. H. (2022). Functional activation of insula and dorsal anterior cingulate for conflict control against larger monetary loss in young adults with subthreshold depression: a preliminary study. *Scientific Reports*, *12*(1), 6956. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-10989-0>
- Zhang, Y., Huang, C.-C., Zhao, J., Liu, Y., Xia, M., Wang, X., Wei, D., Chen, Y., Liu, B., Zheng, Y., Wu, Y., Chen, T., Cheng, Y., Xu, X., Gong, Q., Si, T., Qiu, S., Cheng, J., Tang, Y., ... Lo, C.-Y. Z. (2024). Dysfunction in sensorimotor and default mode networks in major depressive disorder with insights from global brain connectivity. *Nature Mental Health*, *2*(11), 1371–1381. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44220-024-00323-0>
- Zheng, K., Chen, L., Wang, H., Li, B., & Chen, B. (2026). Beyond depression symptoms: the default mode network as a predictor of antidepressant response. *Npj Mental Health Research*, *5*(1), 2. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44184-025-00182-2>